

Fear of Failure and Perception of the Motivational Climate Under the Coach Pressure

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Abstract:

The motivational climate perceived by players is a psychosocial process that has an impact on how they adjust their psychological response to performance situations with greater or lesser efficiency and balance. The aim of this study was to identify distinctive profiles of fear of failure and basic psychological needs in young handball players according to perceived motivational climate (mastery vs. performance). It examined differences in the distribution of gender and age and satisfaction of basic psychological needs and fear of failure within each profile. The study participants were 681 young ($M = 16.16$ years; $SD = 0.92$) handball players. A battery of scales adapted to Spanish was administered to measure motivational climate, fear of failure, and basic psychological needs. Central tendency, correlational, cluster, and comparative analysis (MANOVA) were applied to determine two profiles (Cluster 1 vs. Cluster 2). The Cluster 1 was characterized by those players with the highest values in the perception of a mastery climate, and the Cluster 2 included those players with a mixed mastery/performance climate. The results may provide relevant information suggesting that a climate high in mastery and performance is preferable to a climate that is moderately high in both dimensions. They are useful to coaches in designing and adjusting training programs so that their athletes can enhance resources under balanced psychological efforts that reduce discomfort and flight, thus improving adaptation skills to coping with competitive demands and pressure.

Keywords: coaches; shame; handball; well-being; psychological adjustment; young athletes.

1 **Fear of Failure and Perception of the Motivational Climate Under the** 2 **Coach Pressure**

3 **Introduction**

4 During the player's training process, competition becomes a context of ability and
5 achievement, in which the athlete tries to achieve success by demonstrating his or her
6 skills, abilities, and competencies.^{1,2} When this environment favors the learning of
7 behaviors and attitudes that involve responsibility, eagerness to excel, and self-control,
8 sports practice contributes to the psychological, personal, and social development of the
9 athlete.³

10 On the other hand, and especially in highly competitive contexts, sport is also a
11 means through which athletes can perceive they are not very competent in front of their
12 peers⁴, generating public exposure before others, where athletes often experience fear
13 of failure, in which their performance is evaluated by external agents (e.g., the coach)
14 based on criteria usually based on performance and success.⁵

15 Fear of failure is understood as the stable tendency to anticipate shame and
16 humiliation after failure.⁶⁻⁸ Theoretical frameworks^{5-6,9}, define that this fear of failure
17 appears when the athlete allows others to be in charge of controlling/evaluating his/her
18 behavior over his/her self-evaluation and introspection processes, seeking approval
19 from such external evaluators and/or fearing disapproval. Therefore, it is very important
20 that the athlete learns and possesses the ability to manage and control these types of
21 situations since poor management of these can lead to errors or mistakes.¹⁰⁻¹¹ Therefore,
22 feeling and perceiving psychological vulnerability close to making mistakes in highly
23 competitive sports practice promotes in the athlete the fear of failure, feeling of shame
24 that would cause insecurity, anxiety, and even blocking or freezing of thoughts that
25 deriving in cognitive errors (e.g., lack of concentration, high self-criticism) or avoidance
26 behaviors (e.g., conflict with others, simulate injuries), especially close and during
27 competition and influencing a relevant reduction in health (or wellbeing) and
28 performance.^{10,12} Therefore, fear of failure is a feeling with environmental antecedents
29 and consequences on behavior, which can be perceived and interpreted by athletes in
30 multiple ways and, therefore, can also affect them differently depending on time,
31 context, and relationship.^{13,14}

32 In the sports context, the importance of significant agents, and especially the
33 figure of the coach,¹⁵ must be highlighted, as it is essential in the construction of
34 motivational climates.¹⁶ To analyze the impact of their influence on athletes'
35 psychological adjustment, two of the most argued theoretical approaches are the Self-
36 Determination Theory (SDT)^{17, 18} and the Achievement Goals Theory (AGT)^{19, 20}. The
37 latter theory considers that, in a purposive way, people organize their efforts (including
38 behaviors, cognitions, and emotions) to achieve a given goal, either towards the
39 attainment of internal drives (ego) satisfaction or towards the valuation of the learning
40 that such goal orientation entails (task). Taken to the world of sport, this approach
41 analyzes the psychological adjustment of athletes from both perspectives in the focus
42 both well-being and performance, which are not mutually exclusive but coexistent.

43 According to AGT and SDT, when the coaches value the effort and attitudinal
44 improvement of their athletes, they focus their attention on aspects of learning taking
45 into account their point of view, promoting positive personal relationships, favoring the
46 development of a mastery-oriented climate, and enjoying more the sports learning
47 process, thus promoting the satisfaction of psychological basic needs (competence,
48 autonomy, and social relationships). In contrast, when the coaches put emphasis on the
49 result, punishing mistakes, prioritizing successes as the only way to reinforce progress,
50 or are not concerned about the personal relationships among their athletes, they favor a
51 performance-oriented climate and the basic psychological needs of his players are not
52 satisfied.^{21, 22} Literature has shown that a task-involvement motivational climate or
53 mastery-oriented climate promotes a higher level of self-esteem, satisfaction, well-
54 being, adherence, and enjoyment with sports practice among athletes,^{23, 24} whereas an
55 ego-oriented motivational climate or a performance-oriented climate is linked to
56 anxiety, burnout, conflict^{25, 26}, poorer emotional management and difficulties in sports
57 learning.¹² Ames²⁷ introduced the terms mastery climate and performance climate, to
58 describe the environment that favors or generates the coach in the sports context.

59 In team sports, it has been shown that depending on the behavior adopted by the
60 coach during the training stages, the way he/she interacts with his/her athletes, and the
61 motivational climate he/she favors, fear of failure, satisfaction, and continuity with
62 sports practice are facilitated or impaired,¹² as well as the satisfaction/frustration of
63 basic psychological needs, the degree of motivation, involvement, and commitment of
64 the athlete.^{21, 28} In this way, it is possible to differentiate coaching behaviors that

65 conform to a more controlling style versus one that is more supportive of athlete
66 autonomy.^{29, 30}

67 Literature has shown that more controlling styles impair and impede the
68 satisfaction of basic psychological needs, decreasing the well-being of athletes or
69 causing them to have a less positive experience, whereas styles that support autonomy
70 favor perceptions of competence, social bonds, self-esteem, and cohesion of team
71 members.³¹

72 Therefore, it can be stated that team sport is a context conducive to social
73 interaction, full of psychological responses, and in constant interaction between the
74 different protagonists of the sports situation (e.g., players, coaches, team). Such
75 processes must be effectively managed by the coach as the person in charge of the
76 search for the "psychosocial balances" necessary for the improvement of both individual
77 and group performance.³²

78 Attending therefore to the literature reviewed, the objectives of the present study
79 were to identify different distinctive profiles (clusters) of young handball players
80 according to the perceived motivational climate favored by their coach, examining their
81 differences according to gender, age, satisfaction of basic psychological needs and fear
82 of failure. The study hypotheses expected that those who perceived a more
83 performance-oriented climate would show higher indicators of fear of failure and lower
84 satisfaction of basic psychological needs (and linked to more rigid or not very rational
85 profiles), while those who perceived a more mastery-oriented climate would show
86 lower effects of fear of failure and higher satisfaction of basic psychological needs
87 (linked to more reflective and flexible profiles).

88 **Method**

89 *Participants*

90 A total of 681 team sports players belonging to different clubs in Spain participated
91 (391 boys, 57.4%; 290 girls, 42.6%), with an average age of 16.16 years (SD = 0.92).
92 According to age, 20.9% (n = 142) of the participants were <15 years old, while 79.1%
93 (n = 539) were >15 years old. Most of them stated that they had more than 5 years of
94 sports experience (75.5%, n = 514) and they spent more than two trainings/week
95 (96.3%, n = 656) and more than 3 hours/week (90.3%, n = 615). The level of
96 competition for all players is regional. The first places in the regional leagues then

97 compete for the national finals of the Spanish Championship. Table 1 reflects the
 98 distribution according to the frequency and duration of weekly sports practice and the
 99 federated sports experience of the players.

100 Table 1. Socio-demographic and sporting characteristics of participants.

		N	%
Gender	Boys	391	57.4%
	Girls	290	42.6%
Age-Game Category	Cadets (14-15 years old)	142	20.9%
	Youth (16-17 years old)	539	79.1%
Sports Experience	up to 5 years	167	24.5%
	more than 5 years	514	75.5%
Trainings/Week	Up to 2 trainings/week	25	3.7%
	More than 2 trainings/week	656	96.3%
Training Hours/Week	Up to 3 hours/week	66	9.7%
	More than 3 hours/week	615	90.3%

101

102 *Instruments*

103 Perceived Motivational Climate in Sport Questionnaire (PMCSQ-2).^{22, 33} This is a
 104 questionnaire that assesses athletes' perception of the motivational climate created by
 105 the coach. The Spanish version^{34, 35} was validated in Spanish elite female senior
 106 handball players and includes 29 items grouped in two dimensions measuring the
 107 performance-oriented climate (14 items, e.g. "On this team, the coach gives most of his
 108 or her attention to the stars"), and the mastery-oriented climate (15 items, e.g. "On this
 109 team, the coach emphasizes always trying to do your best"). Responses were provided
 110 on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The
 111 internal consistency analysis was satisfactory for the two subscales mastery ($\alpha = .85$),
 112 and competitive ($\alpha = 0.83$).

113 Performance Failure Appraisal Inventory (PFAI).⁷ This scale consists of 25
 114 items measuring beliefs associated with aversive consequences of failure. The Spanish
 115 long version⁹ was applied to basketball players (12 to 16 years old). This version
 116 includes the items grouped in five dimensions: Fear of Experiencing Shame and
 117 Embarrassment (e.g., "When I am not succeeding, I am less valuable than when I
 118 succeed"), Fear of Devaluing One's Self-estimate (e.g., "When I am failing, I blame my
 119 lack of talent"), Fear of Having an Uncertain Future (e.g., "When I am failing, my
 120 future seems uncertain"), Fear of Important Others Losing Interest (e.g., "When I am

121 not succeeding, people are less interested in me”), and Fear of Upsetting Important
122 Others (e.g., “When I am failing, it upsets important others”). Responses were provided
123 on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (do not believe at all) to 5 (believe 100% of the
124 time). Here the internal consistency analysis was satisfactory for the different sub-
125 scales; fear of experiencing shame and embarrassment, $\alpha = 0.84$; fear of devaluing
126 one’s self-esteem $\alpha = 0.70$; fear of having an uncertain future, $\alpha = 0.65$; fear of
127 important others losing interest, $\alpha = 0.86$; fear of upsetting important others, $\alpha = 0.84$.
128 The "fear of having an uncertain future" factor showed less reliability than the
129 recommended value of 0.70, and it should be considered as a study limitation.

130 Basic Psychological Needs in Exercise Scale (BPNES).³⁶ This questionnaire
131 seeks analyze the satisfaction of basic psychological needs in physical exercise. The
132 Spanish version³⁷ was validated in a sample of people who practiced physical exercise
133 regularly (16 to 53 years old). It includes 12 items divided into three dimensions, with
134 four items per dimension, to assess autonomy (e.g., “The way I exercise is in agreement
135 with my choices and interests”), competence (e.g., “I feel I perform successfully the
136 activities of my exercise programme”), and relatedness (e.g., “My relationships with the
137 people I exercise with are close”). Responses were provided on a 5-point Likert scale
138 ranging from 1 (I don’t agree at all) to 5 (I completely agree). The internal consistency
139 analysis was satisfactory for the three subscales: autonomy ($\alpha = 0.60$), competence ($\alpha =$
140 0.64), and relatedness ($\alpha = 0.74$). The "autonomy" and “competence” factors showed
141 less reliability than the recommended value of .70 and they should be considered as a
142 study limitation.

143 ***Procedure***

144 The study was carried out in different handball clubs of Spain. A letter explaining the
145 objectives of the research and how it was to be carried out, accompanied by two models
146 of informed consent and permission (one for the parents and another for the young
147 athletes), together with a copy of the measures, was sent to the clubs before the data
148 collection. The questionnaire was administered by the researchers in the sports facilities
149 of the clubs during the training sessions and completed by the participants in 20-30 min.
150 All the participants were informed of the objectives and of their rights as participants in

151 the study, as well as of the voluntary nature and the absolute confidentiality of the
152 answers and handling of the data. It was explained that there were no correct or
153 incorrect answers so that participants would answer with the most sincerity and honesty.
154 Data were collected in February 2023. Once all the data had been collected, they were
155 transferred to the Excel 2010 program for subsequent treatment in the SPSS 23.0
156 statistical analysis program. The protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee of the
157 Universidad de Murcia (ID: 1494/2017). All subjects gave written informed consent in
158 accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.³⁸

159 *Statistical analysis*

160 Following previous studies, the following process was carried out.^{39, 40} First, a reliability
161 analysis of all the scales was performed and then the Mahalanobis distance was used in
162 order to detect and eliminate those subjects who were atypical or did not follow a
163 logical pattern in the set of variables. In addition, skewness and kurtosis values (> 3 or $>$
164 10 respectively) were analyzed, together with Z-scores (> 3). After eliminating 26
165 subjects who did not meet these requirements, the reliability analysis of the different
166 scales was again carried out, finally having a total sample of 681 subjects, the reliability
167 analysis of the different scales was again carried out and a descriptive and correlation
168 analysis was started.

169 Secondly, according to the first objective of this study, to identify clusters of
170 athletes on the basis of the perceived motivational climate, a profile analysis (cluster)
171 was performed using the coach's motivational climate (Cluster 1 or Cluster 2) as an
172 independent variable. To determine the number of profiles, a dendrogram analysis was
173 first performed using the hierarchical method (Ward procedure) with Squared Euclidean
174 distance between observations as the dissimilarity measure suggesting the development
175 of two to four sets. Next, a two-stage clustering corroborated a silhouette measure of
176 cohesion and cluster separation considered as good (> 0.5) for two sets. Finally, the K-
177 means method was used to make the final clusters with 2 clusters.

178 Finally, to answer the second purpose and examine the differences according to
179 gender and category in basic psychological needs and fear of failure, a multivariate

180 analysis (MANOVA) was carried out to check whether there were statistically
181 significant differences in each of the variables under investigation and subsequently,
182 univariate analysis (ANOVA) were performed according to the differences found in
183 each of the variables under investigation. In addition, the clusters were analyzed
184 according to gender and grouped age by means of a chi-square analysis with 2x2
185 contingency tables. Statistical analysis was performed using the IBM SSPS 23.0
186 package. This established a level of significance of $p < 0.05$.

187 **Results**

188 *Descriptive and correlation analysis*

189 Table 2 shows the descriptive analyses of the different variables under study. Skewness
190 and kurtosis values showed adequate values (< 3 skewness and < 10 kurtosis). Finally,
191 correlations were significant at $p < 0.001$ except for competition and fear of angering
192 others which was at $p < 0.05$. The variables that had no correlation were the
193 performance climate with autonomy and competence, in addition to autonomy with all
194 causes of fear of failure except with the scale of experiencing embarrassment. The
195 mastery climate had an inverse correlation with the execution climate and fear of
196 failure, as well as a direct correlation with basic psychological needs. In contrast, the
197 performance climate showed an inverse correlation with social relations and a direct
198 correlation with fear of failure.

199 *Cluster analysis*

200 Cluster analysis was performed according to the considerations of Hair, Anderson ⁴¹.
201 The dendrogram obtained suggested the existence of two clusters. Finally, the existence
202 of two types of athlete profiles was suggested. The clusters were grouped into Cluster 1
203 ($N = 350$; 51.4%), with statistically significant higher values in the mastery climate and
204 lower values in the performance climate, and Cluster 2 ($n = 331$; 48.6%) with moderate
205 scores above the midpoint on both the mastery and performance subscales. The values
206 were in the mastery climate of 4.31 ($SD = .44$) and 3.76 ($SD = 0.57$) for Cluster 1 and
207 Cluster 2 respectively and for the performance climate, 2.21 ($SD = 0.40$) and 3.32 (SD
208 $= .48$) for Cluster 1 and Cluster 2 respectively, indicating the profiles after transforming
209 the values obtained into Z scores (figure 1). The significance level was $p = 0.00$ in both
210 cases.

Table 2. Descriptive and correlations analysis.

		<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>K</i>	α	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	Mastery climate	4.05	0.58	-0.685	0.289	0.853		-0.281**	0.277**	0.465**	0.294**	-0.185**	-0.147**	-0.202**	-0.321**	-0.264**
2	Performance climate	2.75	0.71	0.252	-0.396	0.836			-0.043	-0.128**	-0.034	0.305**	0.326**	0.339**	0.438**	0.393**
3	Autonomy	3.83	0.66	-0.073	-0.567	0.603				0.437**	0.570**	-0.110**	-0.038	-0.024	-0.067	-0.056
4	Relatedness	4.27	0.66	-0.707	-0.290	0.744					0.514**	-0.188**	-0.150**	-0.200**	-0.338**	-0.309**
5	Competence	3.98	0.62	-0.310	-0.256	0.635						-0.139**	-0.122**	-0.106**	-0.127**	-0.095*
6	Fear experiencing shame embarrassment (F1)	2.61	0.92	0.161	-0.719	0.841							0.702**	0.607**	0.614**	0.618**
7	Fear devaluing ones self estimate (F2)	2.49	0.88	0.279	-0.365	0.701								0.677**	0.599**	0.626**
8	Fear having uncertain future (F3)	2.27	0.84	0.603	0.082	0.654									0.697**	0.709**
9	Fear important other losing interest (F4)	2.01	0.91	0.774	-0.099	0.862										0.809**
10	Fear upsetting important others (F5)	2.10	0.91	0.652	-0.364	0.842										

Note. ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$

1

2

3 Figure 1. Cluster Z values for the different variables.

4 ***Differences in profiles according to basic psychological needs and fear of***
 5 ***failure***

6 A multivariate analysis (MANOVA) was carried out using the clusters as independent
 7 variables and the rest of the study variables as dependent variables (see Table 3). Box's
 8 test was used to test for homogeneity of covariance (Box's $M = 72.451$; $F = 1.988$; $p =$
 9 0.00). Statistically significant differences were found at the multivariate level (Wilks'
 10 $\Lambda = 0.802$, $F = 20.741$, $p = 0.00$). The results of the follow-up univariate test as
 11 part of the MANOVA are also presented (see Table 3), showing significant differences
 12 for each of the variables analyzed. Cluster 1 obtains higher values for all the basic
 13 psychological needs, while Cluster 2 shows higher values in each of the fear of failure
 14 variables.

15 Table 3. Differences in profiles according to basic psychological needs and fear of
 16 failure.

	Cluster 1 (High mastery/Low performance)		Cluster 2 (Mixed mastery/performance)		<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
Autonomy	3.91	0.66	3.75	0.66	10.632	0.001**
Relatedness	4.42	0.61	4.11	0.67	39.807	0.000**
Competence	4.06	0.59	3.90	0.64	12.770	0.000**
Fear experiencing shame embarrassment (F1)	2.35	0.87	2.87	0.90	58.931	0.000**

Fear devaluing ones self estimate (F2)	2.23	0.78	2.77	0.89	68.236	0.000**
Fear having uncertain future (F3)	2.00	0.69	2.56	0.90	82.928	0.000**
Fear important other losing interest (F4)	1.64	0.71	2.41	0.93	148.542	0.000**
Fear upsetting important others (F5)	1.78	0.73	2.45	0.96	104.598	0.000**

M de box = 72.451 (f = 1.988) p = 0.000

Lamda de Wilks (λ) = 0.802 (f = 20.741) p = 0.000

17 Note. M = Mean; SD = Standard deviation; ** p < 0.01

18 *Differences in profiles according to the age and gender of the players*

19 Next, a univariate analysis (ANOVA) was performed using the cluster as a fixed factor
 20 and gender on the one hand, and grouped age on the other hand, as dependent variables.
 21 Differences were found according to gender (F = 17.875; P = 0.000; R² = 0.260), but
 22 not according to the age of the participants (F = 0.563; P = 0.453; R² = 0.001) (Table 4).
 23 According to the gender of the participants, statistically significant differences were
 24 found in the clusters found.

25 Cluster 1 was positively associated with women (60.7% vs. 44.5% of men) and
 26 cluster 2 with men (55.5% vs. 39.3% of women), suggesting that men obtained a profile
 27 more related to the performance climate, and women to the mastery climate.

28 Table 4. Differences in profiles according to the age and gender of the players.

		Cluster 1 (n = 350) 51.4%		Cluster 2 (n = 331) 48.6%	
		n	%	n	%
Gender	Boys	174	44,5%	217	55,5%
	Girls	176	60,7%	114	39,3%
	F				17.875
	p				.000**
Age-Game Category	Cadets	69	48,6%	73	51,4%
	Youth	281	52,1%	258	47,9%
	F				0.563
	p				0.453

29 Note. ** p < 0.001

30 **Discussion**

31 The objectives of the present study were to identify the distinctive profiles (clusters) of
 32 young players according to the perceived motivational climate favored by the coaches
 33 and to examine their differences according to gender, age, satisfaction of basic
 34 psychological needs, and fear of failure. The hypotheses sought confirm that those
 35 athletes that perceived a mastery climate showed more adaptive psychological

36 functionality and those that perceived a performance climate showed more disadaptive
37 psychological response.

38 The results of the descriptive analysis showed that most of the players were
39 characterized by perceiving a climate of mastery in training and competitions, by
40 feeling their basic psychological needs satisfied, especially that of social relationships,
41 and by showing that shame is the main aversive cause of fear of failure. Therefore, this
42 data allow confirm the hypotheses formulated.

43 In relation to the perception of motivational climate, the results coincide with
44 previous studies that followed a similar trend, also conducted in team sports and with
45 similar samples.^{21, 28, 42, 43, 44} The literature so far has shown that coaches who transmit a
46 climate of mastery in their players encourage effort, interest in learning, progression,
47 and self-improvement through comparison with oneself to assess their level of
48 competence, the development of their skills, and cooperation among team
49 components.^{45, 46} Likewise, different studies also reflected those athletes subjected to
50 this type of motivational climate increased their satisfaction and enjoyment with sports
51 practice²⁸ and decreased fear of failure and competitive anxiety.^{12, 47}

52 On the other hand, we find those players who train under an performance
53 climate, suffer from higher levels of both fear of failure and anxiety and lower
54 satisfaction with the practice of their sport.^{12, 47, 48} This climate promotes social
55 comparison as the basis for success, and rewards, which are based on the demonstration
56 of performance, are established in a public manner.⁴⁶

57 *The relevant construction of the climate by the coach-player dyad*

58 Literature has also shown that the motivational climate favored by the coach
59 influences motivation through the satisfaction of basic psychological needs.⁴⁹ Alesi,
60 Gómez-López²⁵ model (with a similar handball players sample) showed that basic
61 psychological needs mediated between mastery climate and self-determined motivation,
62 and the latter between needs and sport commitment. Specifically, mastery climate
63 positively predicted the self-determination index and sport commitment, through the
64 satisfaction of basic psychological needs.

65 The satisfaction or frustration of basic psychological needs will determine a
66 series of consequences at both cognitive, affective and behavioral levels.⁵⁰ In this case,
67 as already emphasized by Deci and Ryan¹⁸, social relatedness (degree to which players
68 seek interaction, a sense of belonging and connection with the rest of the teammates) is
69 the psychological substrate alluded to by most of the athletes in this study, and it is

70 possible to consider it as the key aspect built by a mastery and autonomy-fostering
71 climate. Previous studies highlighted that the practitioners of collective sports were
72 favored over those of individual modalities in the perception of competence.⁵¹

73 Likewise, embarrassment appears among the results found as the negative cause
74 most alleged by adolescent athletes facing a competitive environment where they have
75 to prove their worth and skill in the game under the direct evaluation of their coach,
76 peers, and/or parents. Literature has shown that the most frequent aversive cause of fear
77 of failure is embarrassment.^{51,52,53} In fact, Sagar and Stoeber⁵⁴ reflected that the only
78 significant predictor in relation to fear of failure was fear of experiencing
79 embarrassment. Recent studies have revealed that fear of experiencing embarrassment is
80 associated with high levels of psychological stress⁵⁵ and competitive anxiety.^{12, 56}
81 Likewise, coaches who foster a climate of mastery consider mistakes as part of the
82 players' learning in their formative process, thus favoring the way players cope with this
83 feeling, which decreases their fear of failure.^{9,47}

84 *Psychological functionality of the players, and its correspondence in the adaptation to*
85 *the demands of training*

86 When training contexts are exposed (independently of the generation of
87 mastery-oriented or performance-oriented climates), it is of great importance to check
88 the "psychological behavior" of the players. This will shape the way they function under
89 the rules, routines and strategies proposed by the team management. Regardless of its
90 initial positive or negative appreciation, the function of the psychological response (e.g.,
91 fear of failure, extra involvement in the tasks) is the symptom of psychological
92 processes (e.g., embarrassment at being evaluated or punished in public, need to please)
93 that must necessarily be attended to, trained and observed so that its evolution (from
94 positive to negative or vice versa) can generate the least distortion or discomfort in the
95 athlete.

96 The cluster analysis offered the existence of two clearly differentiated profiles of
97 players. The so-called Cluster 1 (more functional) is made up mostly of girls and with a
98 high perception of mastery climate and low of performance climate, and on the other
99 hand, Cluster 2 (more dysfunctional), with a majority of boys and a mixed
100 mastery/performance climate. These results coincided with those found in other
101 previous study conducted with handball players, in which the perception of performance
102 climate is higher in boys.²¹

103 The results of the study also showed that for both profiles of athletes the least
104 satisfied basic psychological need is autonomy, in contrast to social relationships where
105 satisfaction levels were higher in the group of Cluster 1 athletes. This result contrasts
106 radically with classic studies on basic psychological needs in athletes. Deci and Ryan¹⁸
107 defined the psychological substrate autonomy as being the origin or source of one's own
108 behavior. In any context, people tend to get involved in the tasks they perform if they
109 consider that they have some control over the environment and allow them to develop
110 their capabilities.^{57, 58} Therefore, an interpersonal style that promotes autonomy will
111 favor the satisfaction of basic psychological needs.⁵⁷ To promote autonomy, the coach
112 should be flexible, accept opinions, show empathy with the players, and provide
113 adequate information during training sessions.⁵⁹ Controlling coaches are usually
114 coercive and authoritarian.⁶⁰ This coach profile orients sports practice to performance
115 and focuses more on developing their ideas than on attending to the needs, satisfaction,
116 or well-being of their athletes.⁶¹ Literature has shown that a controlling style is
117 positively related to the perception of a motivational climate of performance.⁵⁸

118 Regarding the different aversive causes of the fear of making a mistake during
119 the game, the levels were higher in all causes in Cluster 2 players, with shame being the
120 one with the highest score, followed by a devaluation of self-esteem.⁶² This feeling of
121 shame creates in athletes a certain degree of insecurity, anxiety stress, and avoidance
122 behaviors, due to what others may say or think, especially during the game, thus causing
123 a decrease in the player's performance.⁹ Conroy, Poczwardowski⁶ defined fear of
124 failure as a stable tendency to anticipate embarrassment and humiliation after failure.

125 Although the results found on the fear of failure according to the gender of the
126 athletes are scarce, the literature reveals that boys present a greater fear of making a
127 mistake than girls,^{47, 63} thus coinciding with the results found in the study. These results
128 differ from those found by Amiryan, Hejazi Dinan⁶⁴ where girls experienced greater
129 fear of failure than boys. If we analyze the different causes, Gómez-López, Ruiz-
130 Sánchez⁴⁷ and Correia, Rosado⁵² revealed that girls presented higher values for fear of
131 experiencing embarrassment and fear of self-devaluation, and lower values for fear of
132 having an uncertain future, losing the interest of others, and disturbance to significant
133 others than men. On the other hand, Sagar and Jowett⁵³ showed that boys experienced
134 less fear of self-esteem devaluation than girls.

135 *Limitations and new research focuses*

136 With regard to the limitations of the study, it should be noted that although the
137 results extend the information that exists and has been published so far, the specificity
138 and selection of the sample examined, which was intentional, limits its generalization.
139 In the future, more replications are needed in other sports levels and other age ranges,
140 covering all ages of adolescence. A second limitation comes from the measurement of
141 the perception of motivational climate. In this sense, contrasting the information
142 obtained with that which could be provided by the coach himself⁶⁵, would provide a
143 value of greater objectivity between what was observed at the different levels of the
144 sports situation studied (young athletes and coaches). It would also be interesting to
145 consider in the analysis the six factors that make up the dimensions found to underlie a
146 mastery-oriented climate (Effort/Improvement, Important Role, and Cooperative
147 Learning) and performance-oriented climate (Intra-Team Member Rivalry, Unequal
148 Recognition, and Punishment for Mistakes).

149 In order to focus on new approaches to the research, the interesting and
150 appreciable interactions emerging from the present study between age category and
151 gender, showing differences in perceived motivational climate (although not in age or
152 competitive level), should be the subject of further in-depth studies, as well as their
153 contrast with other typologies of samples of young athletes (individual sports), other
154 sports cultures (e.g., combat sports) or in other countries.

155 Also, we consider that could be important of longitudinal proposals through
156 multilevel studies that take into account certain gaps in the literature. This could provide
157 greater clarity on the correspondences between training styles and the impact on the
158 psychosocial response (internal and external) of their athletes as a function of different
159 sporting circumstances (e.g., streaks of good or bad games, opinions of starting or
160 substitute players) or other personality (e.g., impulsivity, perfectionism, self-esteem) or
161 social (e.g., parental pressure, category transition) influences.

162 Finally, it should be noted that this study provides new and significant
163 information for the coach that will allow him to individualize the treatment of his
164 players. In other words, the results provide relevant information for coaches, as they
165 will help them design individualized training programs that will improve athletes'
166 performance while ensuring their health and well-being. The bibliographic review
167 carried out confirms the scarcity of similar studies published more specifically in
168 basketball and handball. Furthermore, it constitutes a preliminary study to guide future
169 research in which the main objective would be to carry out individualized psychological

170 interventions for coaches to improve satisfaction in the practice of sports by their
171 players.

172 **Conclusions**

173 The line of investigation initiated in this study has important practical
174 repercussions in the design of intervention programs focused on the psychological
175 variables analyzed (satisfaction of basic psychological needs and fear of failure) and
176 their possible determinants with the aim of improving the performance and the quality
177 of life of the sportsmen.

178 In line with the most current views on psychological adaptation and
179 functionality in the social contexts offered by sport, the perception of the motivational
180 climate created by coaches in the locker room and competition situations facilitates and
181 generates that most players focus on a mastery climate in training and competitions,
182 feeling more satisfied their psychological needs (mainly that of social relationship) and
183 reduced their feelings of shame, the main aversive cause of fear of failure. In addition, it
184 favors the appearance of emotional regulation processes and cognitive re-evaluation of
185 errors, doubts or concerns, as well as the meaning of those stressors that have a negative
186 impact (e.g., shame). In contexts where performance-oriented climate (internal drives
187 and extreme needs such as identification or narcissism) and outcome determinism are a
188 priority, the cognitive response (e.g., rumination; obsessivity) of athletes elevates the
189 tendency to repress the drive and extreme desire to "succeed above all else," resulting in
190 processes of emotional maladjustment (e.g., shame, anger, defensive struggle) that
191 inhibit externalized behavior.

192 On the other hand, the cluster analysis offered the existence of two clearly
193 differentiated profiles of players. On the one hand, the so-called Cluster 1, made up
194 mostly of girls and with a higher perception of a mastery climate, and on the other hand,
195 Cluster 2, with a majority of boys and a higher perception of a performance climate. In
196 both profiles, the least satisfied basic psychological need was autonomy, as opposed to
197 social relations, where satisfaction levels were higher in the group of Cluster 1 players.
198 As for the different aversive causes of the fear of making a mistake during the game, the
199 levels were higher in all causes in the Cluster 2 players, with shame being the one with
200 the highest score, followed by a devaluation of self-esteem. These results do suggest
201 that a climate high in mastery and low in performance is preferable to a climate that is
202 moderately high in both dimensions.

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208 Data are available from the authors on request.

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